

PHARMACEUTICAL STUDY ON RASAKARPURA BY VIDHYADHARA YANTRA METHOD

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Article Received on 16 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 06 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 15 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949919>

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How to cite this Article: Anagha K.*¹, Asha P. N.2. (2025). PHARMACEUTICAL STUDY ON RASAKARPURA BY VIDHYADHARA YANTRA METHOD. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 590-596. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Rasashastra, the branch of ayurveda which mainly deals with the preparation of rasoushadhis which are known for its quicker action in smaller quantity. Rasakarpura is a mercurial preparation. There are different 53 methods for the preparation of Rasakarpura by different methods like kupipakwa rasayana, vidhyadhara yantra method, damaru yantra method etc. Different opinions about mercuric chloride, mercurous chloride or mixture of both as chemical composition of final product are available in classical books of ayurveda. *Rasakarpura* has better antimicrobial properties according to the studies. Details concerning rasakarpura's pharmaceutical preparation by vidhyadhara yantra method and its properties will be discussed in the full paper.

KEYWORDS: Rasashastra, rasakarpura, mercuric chloride, mercurous chloride, kupipakwa rasayana, vidhyadhara yantra, antimicrobial.

INTRODUCTION

Rasakarpura is a mercurial preparation which is mentioned in many rasashastra text books by different acharyas. There are different 53 methods for the preparation of Rasakarpura by different methods like kupipakwa rasayana, vidhyadhara yantra method etc.

Rasakarpura is chloride salts of mercury along with trace elements. It is a Nir gandha (without Gandhaka) type of formulation. Rasakarpura is first time mentioned in Rasa Prakasha Sudhakara by the name of 'Ghanasara Rasa' in 12th century AD. While in Bhava Prakasha, it is mentioned that, Rasakarpura is the choice of drug for treatment of Upadamsha (syphilis). Rasa Kamadhenu considers, Rasa Karpura as Heeraka dyuthi sankasham, ie, Heerakabha sphatikakara parada ghanija (Mercurous Chloride Calomal). Availability of this in ghanija form is very rare. Thus Acharya prepared it by using rasayanika vidhi and named it as Rasa Karpura. Appearance of Rasa Karpura is similar to Karpura. The only difference is that Rasa Karpura is Gandha rahitha whereas Karpura is Sugandhayuktha. Acharya Yashodharaji in his text described Rasakarpura as "Ghanasara Rasa" and included under Shweta Rasa Bhasma. The word Rasakarpura comprise of two words, 'Rasa' and 'Karpura'. Rasa means Parada and Karpura means a substance which is white in colour/The substance resembles appearance of Karpura.

There are different types of Rasakarpura preparation by using different mineral, metal and herbal drugs, though the ingredients are different along with Parada the final outcome is almost similar in nature. Different Yantras are mentioned for the preparation of Rasakarpura like valuka yantra, vidhyadhara yantra, damaruyantra and some mushas. Among most widely practiced are valuka yantra i.e kupipakwa preparation that is Bahirdhumavidi and Damaruyantra which is Antardhuma vidhi.

In the present study we have taken vidhyadhara yantra method of preparation of Rasakarpura as per rasakamadhenu.^[1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Method- Vidhyadhara yantra method

Table 1: Ingredients.

Ingredients	Quantity
Shu. Parada	75 g
Shu. Kasisa	25 g
Saindhava lavana	25 g
Shu. Khatika	25 g

Shu. Khatika

METHOD OF PREPARATION

- 1 part of kasisa, khatika and saindhava lavana is taken in powder form and it is added with 3 parts of shu. Parada and mardana has to be done for 1 day.
- Place it in a vidhyadhara yantra and mandhagni is given. For 1 day.
- After swangasheeta the sandhibandhana is carefully removed and the product is collected from the upper pot with tamra patra.

Procedure

Poorva Karma

- * Collection of upakaranas
- * Preparation of mixture
- * Preparation of vidhyadhara yantra: To prepare Vidhyadhara Yantra two are taken, in one pot Place the mixture and sandibandana should be performed by placing another pot over the mixture containing pot.

Pradhana Karma

- * Vidhyadhara Yantra Sthapana: it should be placed exactly in the centre of the Valukayantra, and sand should cover it evenly by all sides, upper pot should be exposed out, so that it should get homogenous temperature and some authors mentions that it can be placed directly on the chullika. Cold pad application should be done over the upper pot.
- * Heating pattern and temperature measurement. Temperature should be maintained as per the indication for the preparation. Duration of heat varies from 3 yama to 12 yama
- * Maintenance of Condensation system Upper part of the upper pot made into cool for condensation by applying cold pad over the upper pot.

Paschat Karma

- * After Swangasitibhavana, vidhyadhara Yantra should be removed from Valukayantra gently and carefully otherwise deposited compound may fall into the lower pot.

- * Sandhimoksana It should be done by knife, carefully by keeping the pots in horizontal position on clean papers. Drug should be scrubbed gently and collected.

OBSERVATIONS

Table 2: Weight of product.

Before mardana	150 g
After mardana	139 g

Table 3: Temperature pattern.

Time	Temperature			
	Flame	Lower pot	Sandhi	Water in upper pot
9.45 AM	230	200.7	54	39
10 AM	277	222.9	69.7	44
11 AM	339	255.4	76	45.5
11.30 AM	358.8	257.9	87	48.7
12 PM	358.8	248	93	48.3
12.30 PM	359	249	94	48.5
1 PM	357.2	243	97	44.1
1.30 PM	370	251	96	45.4
2 PM	376	261.4	98	51.5
2.30 PM	377.4	336	98	49.4
3 PM	379.3	342	99.4	49.9
3.30 PM	376.7	356	104.8	51.7
4 PM	376	363	96	46.3
4.30 PM	376.4	362.7	98	45.6
5 PM	378	398	101.2	47
5.30 PM	369	367	96	45.3
6 PM	367	369	95.5	44.6
6.30 PM	366	372	93	43.1
7 PM	346	378	95	42
7.30 PM	325	359	96	44
8 PM	357	354	94	41.5
8.30 PM	362	389	92	42.9
9 PM	360.9	379	92	44.1
9.30 PM	358	357	91.7	48.6
10 PM	361	362	93	43.6
10.30 PM	363	353	97.4	44.3
11 PM	381	365	94.2	43.9
11.30 PM	345	331	94.6	41.5
12 AM	342	312	74	39.2
12.30 AM	396	354	92	44.6
1 AM	364	336	92.2	47.1
1.30 AM	342.2	308	92.3	42.7
2 AM	364.9	334	92.7	42.9
2.30 AM	378	361	92.3	43.5
3 AM	375	370.4	92.3	41.8

3.30 AM	372	376.2	92.6	44.6
4 AM	377	351.8	94.1	43.2
4.30 AM	376	340	93	44.6
5 AM	376	341	94	43
5.30 AM	375	323	102	42.7
6 AM	365	321	98	41.3
6.30 AM	376	355	94	37.3
7 AM	358	324	101	41
7.30 AM	348	345	99	39
8 AM	346	342	100.8	42
8.30 AM	373	347	92	44.8
9 AM	366	374	98	39.2
9.30 AM	369	357	101.8	42.2
9.45 AM	359	367	92	38

The white shining particles of Rasa kaprura formed at the bottom of upperpot, sandhi region and upper side portion of lower pot.

RESULTS

Table 4.

Rasakarpura obtained	12 g
Product obtained at the bottom of upper pot with globules of parada	32 g
Product at the bottom of lower pot	64 g

Table 5: Properties of Rasakarpura.

Rasa	Kashaya
Karma	Vishaghna, Grahi, Ruchivardhaka, Kriminashaka, Balya.
Virya	Ushna
Doshagnata	Tridoshashamaka
Varna	Shweta
Indications ^[2]	Krimivisha, Twakroga, Raktadosha, Vranasrava, Aruchi, Atisara, Pravahika, Sphota, Mandala, Phiranga, Upadansha, Pama
Dose ^[3]	1/64 – 1/32 Ratti (2 – 4 mg)
Sevan Kala ^[4]	Prata Kala (Morning) and advised till the Vyadi nirharana.
Pathya ^[5]	Vrintaka, Tandula, Patola, Punarnava, Puranashali, Godugdha, Dadhi, Goghrita, Godhuma, Hansodaka, Jeeraka etc
Apathya ^[6]	Kakaradi Gana- kalinga, karavela, kadali, kakamachi, kusumbha, karkoti, kushmanda, karkati
Toxicity of Rasakarpura ^[7]	Rasakarpura is listed in the list of poisonous substance under the Ayurvedic and Unani system of medicine in Schedule E1 of Drug and Cosmetic Rule

DISCUSSION

The Parada Bhasmas are of 4 types i.e Shweta, Rakta, Peeta, Krishna. Rasakarpura is said as one of the example for Shweta Parada bhasma, but it has not having the characteristic features. Duration of agni to be given for the preparation Rasakarpura depends on the ingredients used, method of preparation adopted. In this present study, Vidhyadhara yantra method, the reference from Rasakamadhenu is adopted. Here 139 g product is added in vidhyadhara yantra and finally 12g Rasakarpura is obtained.

CONCLUSION

It is used as a medicine for many of the disease such as phiranga, kusta, upadamsha, vana.atisara, pravahika in dose of 2-4 mg. There are various procedures and instrumentations explained for the preparation of Rasakarpura, as well as different heating patterns are also mentioned, vidhyadhara yantra method is one such procedure.^[8] Rasakarpura mainly indicated in upadamsha, phiranga, atisara, pravahika, kusta externally in the form of oil prepared by using many other drugs. As per modern science Rasakarpura is a combination of mercuric chloride and mercurous chloride.

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